

Studies on Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some New Pyrazolines and *N*-Phenylpyrazolines

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The biological and clinical implications of pyrazoline derivatives¹ have prompted us to synthesise some new types of pyrazolines and *N*-phenylpyrazolines with an aim to study their biological activities.

Hydrazine hydrate and 1-(substituted phenyl)-3-(simple/substituted-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one when refluxed in ethanol yielded² the pyrazolines (1a-e). Similarly, when a mixture of 1-(substituted-phenyl)-3-(simple/substituted-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-ones and phenylhydrazine when refluxed in ethanol and acetic acid yielded^{2,3} *N*-phenylpyrazolines (2a-g).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian FT-80 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

3-(3',5'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(2"-methoxy-1"-naphthyl)-2-pyrazoline (1e): A mixture of 1-(3',5'-dichloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(2-methoxy-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one (3.87 g, 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (1.0 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (25

ml) was refluxed for 6 h. It was then cooled, poured into ice-cold water and the separated solid was washed, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 143°; gave no colouration with concentrated H₂SO₄, indicating absence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl; Knorr colour test positive; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 590–1 610 (C=N), 3 300–3 360 (NH stretch), 1 570 (NH bend), 1 220–1 270 (N–N–C) and 3 190–3 200 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 3.42–3.54 (2H, d, CH₂), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃) 5.87–6.1 (1H, t, CH), 6.9–8.13 (8H, m, ArH) and 11.22 (1H, s, OH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

1-Phenyl-3-(3',5'-dichloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(2''-methoxy-1''-naphthyl)-2-pyrazoline (2g): A mixture of 1-(3',5'-dichloro-2'-hydroxyphenyl)-3-(7-methoxy-1-naphthyl)-2-propen-1-one (3.87 g, 0.01 mol) and phenylhydrazine (0.8 g, 0.1 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) and acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. It was then concentrated, cooled, poured into ice-cold water and the separated solid was washed, dried and crystallised from ethanol using little acetic acid, (68%), m.p. 234°; gave no colouration with concentrated H₂SO₄ indicating absence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 590–1 610 (C=N), 1 210–1 270 (N–N–C) and 3 190–3 200 cm⁻¹ (OH); δ 3.49–3.86 (2H, dd, CH₂), 4.08 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.29 (1H, t, CH), 6.74–7.85 (8H, m, ArH) and 10.87 (1H, s, OH).

Similarly, other compounds were prepared (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity: All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against *Curvularia lunata* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* following the disc-diffusion⁴ and hanging drop⁵ methods with slight modification.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND MICROBIAL ACTIVITY DATA OF PYRAZOLINES (1) AND N-PHENYLPYRAZOLINES (2)*

Compd no.**	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Inhibition zone (mm)		<i>C. lunata</i>		<i>H. oryzae</i>		
				<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	% Germination	Germtube length (μ)	% Germination	Germtube length (μ)	
1a	2'-OH	75	180	10	12	100	320	100	90	
b	2'-OH-5'-Cl	80	145	30	24	90	160	80	82	
c	2'-OH-5'-Br	78	148	18	10	100	270	100	160	
d	2'-OH-4'-CH ₃ -5'-Cl	82	177	17	12	100	440	100	460	
e	2'-OH-3',5'-Cl ₂	80	143	29	21	100	140	100	160	
2a	2'-OH	62	140	12	15	100	250	100	80	
b	2'-OH-5'-CH ₃	64	194	29	32	50	180	40	64	
c	2'-OH-5'-Cl	65	186	32	26	80	140	70	68	
d	2'-OH-5'-Br	60	170	30	17	85	250	75	150	
e	2'-OH-4'-CH ₃ -5'-Cl	62	203	35	20	95	325	28	10	
f	2'-OH-3',5'-Cl ₂	66	199	39	32	40	125	55	240	
g	2'-OH-3',5'-Cl ₂	63	234	31	24	15	25	20	30	
				Chloromycetin	25	—	—	—	—	
				H ₂ O-EtOH (9:1)	—	—	95.0	320	95.0	400

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and halogen analyses. **Ar $\equiv$ 2''-OCH₃-1''-naphthyl for all compounds except 2f (Ar $\equiv$ 1''-naphthyl).

NOTES

The results of inhibition were found to be significant. It was noted that the *N*-phenyl pyrazolines were found to be more inhibitory to both bacteria and fungi than the corresponding pyrazolines.

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References

1. A. BERGE, "Medical Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1970, Part-II, p. 959; H. YAMASHITA, M. ODATE,

- H. IIZUKA, H. KAWAZURA, Y. SHIGA and H. NAMEKAWA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1989, **111**, 23510; S. GORAFFINI and V. PALMO, *J. Cancer Chemother. Rep.*, 1961, **13**, 9; M. S. K. YOUSUFF, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 796; C. D. THRON, *Phytopathology*, 1961, **51**, 77; G. HONSNI and S. F. SAAD, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1975, **86**, 263; N. JAISWAL, R. F. JAISWAL, J. P. BARTHWAL and K. KISHOR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 252; P. KALEKAR, M. SANGWAN and K. NARESH, *Chem Abstr.*, 1981, **94**, 47210.
2. M. S. SHINGARE and H. B. SIDDIQUI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 154.
3. A. E. A. SAMMOUR, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 1067; G. A. HANSON, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1958, **67**, 707 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1959, **53**, 18007).
4. C. H. COLLINS, "Microbiological Methods", Butterworths, London, 1967, p. 364.
5. Y. B. VIBHUTE and S. S. WADJE, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1976 **14**, 724.